

Pain and Pathos of Women During 1947 Partition

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Abstract

The partition of India has been horrific ,gruesome, ghastly that it affected million of women, girls and children. The violence that took during the displacement of place, the exodus tells us of the suffering of women. This paper aims to bring out the pain and pathos of women during 1947 partition through literary narratives like novels, poems and short stories.

Keywords Suffering, Pain, Pathos, Violence, Migration, Displacement etc.

Introduction

The partition of India in 1947 was one of the most tumultuous events in modern history marked by widespread violence, mass displacement and profound human suffering. The impact of partition was not just geopolitical, it served deeply into the personal and communal lives of millions. Among those who suffered the most were women whose stories of aim and resilience are poignantly captured in various literary works.

Objective of study This research paper explores the pain and pathos of women during the partition, drawing on notable novels that being their experiences to the forefront.

Review of Literature The Partition of the Indian Subcontinent (1947), as an action-packed event still continues to haunt not only millions of direct and indirect victims of the event in both the countries - India newline and Pakistan. but also in abroad too. It has a significant impact on the victims who later turn into writers. The historians, researchers, scholars and writers face different kinds of uneasiness newline while dealing with Partition in their courses of work. Due to the underlying complexities newline (socio-political, socio-cultural, and socio-psychological) of the period, the ground of Partition has become so extensive and the event has become so cataclysmic in human history. The vastness of the Partition holocaust and its lasting legacies need an expanded framework for its assessment. Newline This thesis entitled , Partition and the Legacy of Violence : A Study of Select Novels aims to scrutinize critically the cataclysmic division of Indian Subcontinent, its causes and its newline legacies till date through literary representation. This research is basically a socio-political and socio-psychological study in the context of the then underlying anachronistic approach to newline religion instead of modern approach to partition of India and Pakistan.

Main Text

The Historical of Context Partition

The Partition of India resulted in the division of British India into two independent dominions, India and Pakistan. The announcement of partition unleashed a wave of communal violence leading to the displacement of approximately 15 million people and the death of estimated one to two million. Amid this chaos, women faced unprecedented brutality, including abductions , rapes , forced conventions and murders.

Womens Suffering In Literary Narrations

Literature has served as a potent medium to depict the harrowing experiences of during Partition. Several novels stand out for their vivid portrayal of women's suffering and resilience.

"*Train to Pakistan*" by Khushwant Singh is a seminal work that captures the essence of Partition's brutality. The novel is set in Mano Majra, a fictional village on the border of India and Pakistan. Through the character of Nooran, a muslim girl in love with a Sikh boy, Jugga Singh portrays the fear and helplessness of women caught in the crossfire of communal hatred. Nooran's plight symbolises the countless women who were forced to flee their homes, leaving behind their lives and loves

"The world seemed to have

Suddenly gone mad. Nooran clung

to Jugga, her body trembling

with fear. 'what will happen to us ? '

She whispered, her voice choked with

Tears."

Bapsi Sidhwa's "*Ice-Candy Man*" also published as *Lacking India*. Provides a child's perspectives on the horrors of Partitions, the novel's protagonist, Lenny, observes the breakdown of friendship and communities through the eyes of her Ayah, Shanta. Shanta's abduction and subsequent forced marriage to the Ice-Candy Man during this period.

" Shanta's beauty become her

Curse. In a world gone mad, it was

her downfall. They took her, and the

gentle touch of her hands, the

soft ----- of her voice, were

lost to us forever"

Amrita Pritam's '*Pinjar*' (The skeleton) is another poignant tale of partition, focusing on the abduction of Puro, a Hindu girl, by Rashid, a muslim man. The novel delves deeply into Puro's internal struggle and eventual acceptance of fate. Pritam's portrayal of Puro's transformation from a victim to a survivor is both heart-wrenching and empowering.

"Puro looked at herself

in the mirror no longer

seeing the girl who once

dreamed of love and happiness.

She saw a woman forged in

pain , a survivor of the times

standing resilient amidst the

ruins of her past."

Urvashi Butalia's "*The other side of silence*" though not a novel is an essential work that compiles oral histories of Partition survivors , with a significant focus on women's stories. Butalia's work highlights the often histories of partition survivors, with a significant focus

on women's stories. Butalia's work highlights the often overlooked narrative of women who experience the trauma of Partition first hand .Their stories of abduction, violence and survival are crucial to understanding the full impact of this historical event.

"They took us from our homes,
our families, our lives. But in
the silence that followed, we
found our voices. In our pain
we discovered a strength we
never knew we had."

The novel "*Sunlight on the Broken Column*" signifies decay of the Muslim *Taluqdar* family and their traditions. The novel directly does not focus on the partition of India. India's freedom struggle can be seen along with Laila fighting for her personal freedom from the dominant patriarchy.

The novel begins when Laila, the protagonist of the novel is fifteen years of age. It covers the twenty years of India's socio-political life, parallel with Laila's life, beginning from 1932 to 1952. It is divided into four parts. The first part of the novel reveals that Laila is an orphan and is brought up by her paternal aunts Abida who is unmarried and Majida, in her grandfather's home. Baba Jan, patriarch of the family is ill. To take care of him Aunt Abida is shifted to her father's apartment. Soon after Baba Jan's death Aunt Abida is married off and Laila's cousin Zahra, Majida's daughter, is also married off. The two brothers Asad and Zahid, Majida's sons, are sent to other states to pursue education. Laila moves into her uncle's house.

As per the wishes of Laila's deceased father she is permitted to continue western education. Laila like her aunts observes purdah. Laila stops observing purdah in uncle Hamid's care, as he holds liberal ideas. Despite these ideas, Hamid is unable to come out of the family tradition of autocracy.

The second part begins with the new phase of Laila's life. Laila has joined college and made friends. Laila's friends are from different socio-political backgrounds, and this shows the nature of the pre-partition society. The third part presents a conflict in Laila's personal life. Uncle Hamid's two sons, Kemal, an ICS officer and Saleem, a lawyer, returned from England after completing their education. Uncle and Aunt want her to marry any one of their sons. Laila and her cousins do not accept it. Through her cousins Laila is introduced to many people and one among them is Ameer, a lecturer. Laila soon falls in love with him. She plans to pursue her education and joins post-graduation. Her affair with Ameer is disclosed. She goes against the wishes of her family and marries Ameer. In the last section of the novel, that is, in 1952 Laila visits her ancestral home. Through flashback and her memories readers come to know that Ameer is killed during the chaos of India's partition.

"Surely he couldn't die, this powerful man
who lived the lives of so many people for
them, reducing them to fearing automatons" (p.31)

It describes Baba Jan's character and the patriarchal atmosphere in the *Taluqdar* Muslim family that was common in all the households of the time. After Bab Jan's death it is Uncle Hamid who decides the fate of all the family members. The novel is said to be a personal account of Attia Hossain's life. Attia Hussain refrains or does not directly bring in the partition chaos as it is seen in other partition fiction. She depicts the Muslim *Taluqdar* family's routine life. Effect of changing political scenario are seen and heard as well as the partition but it majorly emphasises on the family system and the loss of by gone era. Laila's character is shown in contrast to her female friends and cousins. The freedom to choose a life partner acts as a symbol of freedom that is denied to all the women of the novel. It is Laila who goes against the wishes of her family and writes her own story. Laila gains her personal freedom.

Zahra says "I was brought up to do my duty." (p.147) for Zainab marriage is all about luxurious life "jewels and nice clothes." (p.295) and she says

"Now I serve my mother and father and brothers,
then I'll serve my husband, my father-in-law
and my mother-in-law."

Sita loves Kemal. She considers that love is a personal issue whereas marriage is a public affair. Thus she decides to marry a person of her parents' choice. She says,

"My parents are the best judges of the
man with the best qualifications for
being the husband. They have a wider choice;
it is only love that narrows it down to a pin point. (p.216)...

What has love to do with marriage?

It is like mixing oil and water?

Love is anti-social, while matrimony preserves
the world and its respectability." (p.296)

Laila does not submit to the patriarchal norms and fights for her rights. Marrying a man of her choice is to declare her personal freedom.

The Themes of Pain and Resilience

The novels and narratives on Partition reveal several recurring themes related to women experiences. These include: The Abduction and sexual violence --The abduction and rape of women were tragically common during partition. Women were seen as symbols of community honor , and their violation became a means of inflicting collective shame. In 'Pinjar', Puro's abduction and forced marriage highlight the brutality women faced . And their struggle for agency in a patriarchal society.

Displacement and Loss -- The mass displacement caused by partition uprooted millions from their homes. This loss of homeland and identity is powerfully depicted in "Train to Pakistan", where characters like Nooran face an uncertain future, from their familiar surroundings and loved ones.

Survival and Agency -- Despite the immense suffering ,many women demonstrated remarkable resilience and agency. In "Ice candy man", Shanta's eventual return to her community, though scarred signifies the strength and perseverance of women. Similarly , Puro's transformation in 'Pinjar' from a victim to a woman who forges a new identity for herself is a testament to the indomitable spirit of women during Partition.

The Importance of Remembering Women's Stories -- The pain and pathos of women during Partition are not just historical footnotes but essential components of the larger narratives. Their stories provide a more comprehensive understanding of the human cost of geopolitical decisions. Literature plays a crucial role in preserving these memories and ensuring that the suffering and resilience of women are not forgotten.

By engaging with novels like 'Train to Pakistan', 'Ice candy man', and ' Pinjar', and the works like 'The other Side of Silence', readers gain insight into the multifaceted experiences of women during Partition. These stories compel us to acknowledge the past's horrors and the enduring strength of those who lived through it.

Conclusion The Partition of India cataclysmic event that reshaped the subcontinent's socio-political landscape. Amid the chaos and violence, women bore a disproportionate share of the suffering. Through literature, their stories of pain , loss and resilience came to life, offering poignant reminders of the human cost of conflict. Novels like 'Train to Pakistan',

'Ice-candy man', and 'Pinjar' along with oral histories like 'The Other Side of Silence', are vital in preserving these narratives. They ensure that the voices of women, who endured unimaginable hardships, continue to resonate and remind us of the enduring strength of the human spirit. Thus this research paper highlights the pain and pathos of women during partition of India and Pakistan.

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